

METHODS OF LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE)

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ABSTRACT

The following article is devoted to providing insights into language teaching, particularly the task - based approach to teaching foreign languages. It is crucial for language teachers to come up with the right way and later stick to it to increase the efficiency of the classroom.

Key words: task -based learning, Information gap activity, reasoning gap activity, open-gap activity.

АННОТАЦИЯ

Следующая статья посвящена анализу проблем преподавания иностранных языков, в частности проблемно - ориентированного подхода к обучению иностранным языкам. Очень важно, чтобы учителя языка нашли правильный путь, а затем придерживались его, чтобы повысить эффективность работы класса.

Ключевые слова: обучение на основе задач, деятельность с информационным разрывом, деятельность с рассуждением, деятельность с открытым разрывом.

INTRODUCTION

It is known that there are different types of methods and ways which all have variable effects and usefulness for learners to acquire a subject or a language. Because of being a type of education as important as other one, it isn't possible to decrease the importance of a type from the other ones. There are sorts of educational approaches which give students a chance to feel free and confident during lessons in order to make lessons meaningful. Especially, it is more significant for students to feel free and be sure enough to explain ideas and answer to questions while learning a foreign language by using the language as much as possible in class. Certainly, it depends on teachers to make students think positively to use more the language which is being learned while having lessons and doing different tasks. If teachers make language in the classroom meaningful and therefore memorable, students begin to be interested in doing process language which they are acquiring or recycling in more natural way.

Task-based language teaching (TBLT) is a type of instruction that relies on the use of authentic target language to do meaningful tasks. TBLT is also referred to as task-based instruction (TBI) and can be considered a branch of communicative language teaching (CLT). The notion of tasks is central to this type of instruction. The assessment of learning is mainly based on task outcome and not only on the accurate use of the target language. For this reason, TBLT is believed to be effective in learning target language fluency and developing student confidence.

Task based learning offers students an opportunity to do positive process by using language as much as possible they can. It is naturally to be a such kind of question what actually a task-based learning is. A task-based learning is a learning which focuses on asking students to do more beneficial tasks by using intended language. In task-based learning, all tasks are based on the real tasks which students do them in their daily life. Being like to real life tasks, in this learning such tasks can include like taking an interview, asking help from a responsible person of an organization, visiting travel agency and so on. Students are assessed by considering their task results, in other words according to the completion of the real life tasks rather than the accuracy of the acquiring language forms. It is certain that it makes the task-based learning popular since it helps to develop target language fluency and students confidence for themselves and knowledge.

Task-based language teaching (TBLT), also known as task-based instruction (TBI), focuses on the use of authentic language and on asking students to do meaningful tasks using the target language. Such tasks can include visiting a doctor, conducting an interview, or calling customer service for help. Assessment is primarily based on task outcome (in other words the appropriate completion of real-world tasks) rather than on accuracy of prescribed language forms. This makes TBLT especially popular for developing target language fluency and student confidence. As such, TBLT can be considered a branch of communicative language teaching (CLT).

Task-based language learning has its origins in communicative language teaching, and is a subcategory of it. Educators adopted task-based language learning for a variety of reasons. Some moved to task-based syllabus in an attempt to develop learner capacity to express meaning,[1] while others wanted to make language in the classroom truly communicative, rather than the pseudo-communication that results from classroom activities with no direct connection to real-life situations. Others, like Prabhu in the Bangalore Project, thought that tasks were a way of tapping into learners' natural mechanisms for second-language acquisition, and weren't concerned with real-life communication.

TBLT was popularized by N. S. Prabhu while working in Bangalore, India according to Jeremy Harmer. Prabhu noticed that his students could learn language just

as easily with a non-linguistic problem as when they were concentrating on linguistic questions. Major scholars who have done research in this area include Teresa P. Pica, Martin East, and Michael Long.

Task-based learning focuses on the use of authentic language through meaningful tasks such as visiting the doctor or a telephone call. This method encourages meaningful communication and is student-centred.

Use of learners' own resources

Learners have to use their own linguistic and nonlinguistic resources to complete the task. That is, they have to use whatever knowledge of the language they have in order to participate in the task. Learners may also use nonlinguistic resources such as gestures. This criterion is what makes TBLT unique. In traditional language teaching, the teacher provides the language resources and the students have to master these resources when they do a task. They are not asked to produce communicative messages using their own linguistic resources.

Characteristics:

Students are encouraged to use language creatively and spontaneously through tasks and problem solving

Students focus on a relationship that is comparable to real world activities

The conveyance of some sort of meaning is central to this method

Assessment is primarily based on task outcome

TBLT is student-centered

Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) is the latest trend in SLL approaches. Although it has produced very positive results in certain contexts (eg small class sizes of immigrant children), like every method that has preceded it, TBLT is also revealing its weaknesses. Broady (2006) notes that TBLT may not provide sufficient "Interaction Opportunities." Bruton (2005) identifies other concerns:

There is no acquisition of new grammar or vocabulary features

Everything is left to the teacher

Not all students are or will be motivated by TBLT

Some students need more guidance and will not or cannot 'notice' language forms (grammar) or other elements of accuracy

Students typically translate and use a lot of their L1 rather than the target language in completing the tasks back to top

In general the lesson applying this approach is conducted in three stages:

1. The Pre-Task

This is where you introduce the task to the students, and get them excited for the task. Once they're engaged, then you should set your expectations for the task. Do this so the 'less motivated' students don't do the bare minimum. To do this, you could show

the students an example of the completed task, or model it. If you want to differentiate your students [link], then now is a good time to hand out support materials, or scaffold [link] the task appropriately. Group them and give instructions.

In summary; the focus of the stage is to engage the learners, set expectations and give instructions.

2. The Task

Begin the task! Small groups or pairs are good, rather than a bigger group where shy students can 'hide'. Ideally you won't join in the task, but you'll be monitoring, and only giving hints if students get really stuck. A note here on task design - there are several ways to go about designing a task, but usually (as mentioned above) it should involve a 'gap' of some sort. Read this article for ideas on how to do this.

In summary; the focus of this stage is fluency - using the language to communicate without falling into L1 unless really needed.

3. A Review

Once the learners have completed the task and have something to show, then it's time for a review. Peer reviews are preferable, or if during your monitoring you see an error common to many, a teacher-led delayed correction is also very useful. For weaker groups, peer correction can be made more effective by giving the students support on how to give feedback - perhaps via a checklist, or a 'Things to Look For' list.

In summary; the aim for this stage is accuracy - reflecting on completed work and analyzing it.

Activities which are commonly organized in this kind of language classes:

An information gap task is a technique in language teaching where students are missing information necessary to complete a task or solve a problem, and must communicate with their classmates to fill in the gaps.[1] It is often used in communicative language teaching and task-based language learning. Information gap tasks are contrasted with opinion gap tasks, in which all information is shared at the start of the activity, and learners give their own opinions on the information given.

Reasoning-gap activity. Students receive information, then using the method of reasoning, deduction, logicians use it to complete the task. For example, a student needs to decide which foreign language course to choose - the cheapest, the fastest, or the most innovative - for a teacher-given goal and within given constraints.

Opinion-gap activity. Used to identify personal preferences or exchange views on a specific issue. There is no right or wrong answer for this type of assignment. For example, you give students a story with missing words - different options will only change the meaning of the story, but not the correctness of the answer.

Advantages of the method:

Implicit learning

The aim of TBLT is to help learners develop implicit knowledge of the language that will enable them to participate easily and naturally in communication. The learners get the form and use of the target language without being explicitly being taught. The role of the teacher is to design tasks by replicating and creating the conditions for language learning and for communication that exists outside the confines of the classroom. The aim is that the learners' interlanguage will gain implicit language knowledge while doing tasks.

Incidental learning

Much of our everyday learning is incidental. TBLT provides opportunities for unplanned learning. Completing a real-world task allows the acquisition to take place without any deliberate intention on the part of the learner or the teacher.

Meaningful learning

TBLT allows meaningful communication to occur during the accomplishment of tasks.

Provokes natural language use, spontaneous speech and gives the student realistic scenarios in which to use their knowledge.

Strengthens motivation - a communicative task gives the student a real need for communication, which accumulates knowledge as much as possible.

Centers the lesson on the students and gives them independence in the lesson - the students themselves choose the vocabulary and structures that help to achieve the goal. The teacher's role is to be a guide during the assignment, which allows students to feel independent.

Teaches through actions and interaction - being involved in solving a communicative situation helps students to immerse themselves in the process of learning a language deeper than learning about something.

Disadvantages:

The unpredictability of the lesson. It is difficult to plan such a lesson 100%, to take into account all the necessary vocabulary and structures that students will use during the assignment.

Time consuming. Sometimes the task may take longer than expected. The teacher needs to be flexible and willing to spend more time or adjust the assignment to meet the time limit.

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